

The Historical Expansion of Social Work Education in Tanzania with *Ubuntu* Lens – A Case of *Ujamaa* Intersections Model

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Abstract

Ujamaa intersections model (UIM) guided the literature review on the historical expansion of social work education in Tanzania with Ubuntu lens. Like other pre-colonial African societies, Tanzania's all aspects of life were under Ubuntu philosophy that formed the basis of Indigenous social work education and practice. During colonial rule in Tanzania, colonial legacy underestimated existed Ubuntu education in the country until the post-independence of 1961 when the champion of Ubuntu the late Dr. Julius Nyerere (Ubuntu PhD) restored Ubuntu values and practice into Ujamaa policy framework. Findings have shown that Ujamaa is amid the core value of African Ubuntu, the Ujamaa policy framework succeeded to decolonised education practice in the country through education for self-reliance where integration of Ubuntu into social work education through UIM became realistic. UIM is formed by interchangeable sections in the community namely family, extended families, local leadership, ecology spirituality and wider attributes of community that created advantageous ecology for practical based education. The compatibility of Ujamaa Intersections Model and Social work education supported community development activities, students spent a half of their practical learning into community, community engagement supported to share wisdom, cultural values and actual challenged faced by the community. Overtime Ujamaa contributed on the restoration of the indigenous social work education and UIM has remained a component of social work education in the country. Despite of success of Ujamaa policy framework in restoring and integrating Ubuntu approaches in social work education in the past two decades the Structural Adjustment Policies and globalization has continue to affect the social work education component in the country. Lack of supportive social work legal framework disempowered TASWO and TESWEP into completing the mission of indigenization social work education in the country. It's recommended for endorsement of a single social work policy and comprehensive social work legislation necessary to promote the indigenization of social work education and practice in Tanzania.

Key Words: African social work; African *Ubuntu*; Indigenous social work knowledge; Tanzania social welfare; Tanzania social work education; *Ubuntu*, *Ujamaa Policy*.

INTRODUCTION

In African setting, community is made up by nucleated families that form the basis of Ujamaa intersections model that influences traditional social work education in Tanzania from pre-colonial time (Lembuka, 2024d). *Ujamaa* intersections model was thought to be the right platform to understand the evolution and applicability of both traditional and formal social work education in the country (Lembuka, 2024b). Existence of various sections in the community such as neighbourhood, chieftainship, ecology, spirituality depends on the effectiveness of family thus the essence of traditional social work is compatible with *Ujamaa intersections Model* (Nyerere, 2011). Amid other sections in the community, family remains to be a custodian and key implementer of all indigenous knowledge for the best interests of wider community (Mabeyo, 2014). Most importantly, family connects all major sections in the community towards addressing socio-economic, health and spiritual problems (Nyerere, 2011 & Mugumbate et al, 2013).

Like other African societies, Tanzania's indigenous social work knowledge and practice went undocumented for centuries and the fact that traditional social work education is not well documented so does *Ujamaa Intersections Model*. The practice of social work education in African setting based on the wisdom, cultural values, ecology, geographical location, and economic activities of the respective community intersections. (Lembuka, 2023b). The fact that traditional social work education was practiced across the country from pre-colonial time based on the ecology, communality and cultural perspective that is generally termed as *Ubuntu* (Lembuka, 2023a). Like other pre-colonial African societies family was a main contributor of community welfare and plays a vital role in designing and implementing social work education system in order to address community needs in a humanistic way known as *Ubuntu* (Mugumbate et al, 2020).

Ujamaa is among the core value of Ubuntu, Ubuntu is an African philosophy literary means African humanism or humanness envisioned on collective and holistic approach towards addressing human problems (Mugumbate et al, 2020). Ubuntu represents all African ways of life from pre-colonial time and continues to influence the contemporary African societies including Tanzania (Lembuka, 2023a). Ubuntu and social work are compatible from the vision, mission, values and approaches, more important they both have capacity to influence changes in social, political and economic development (Mugumbate et al, 2013). re-colonial time to the present where respective knowledge is transformed through generations with traditional means such as traditional rituals, oracle, storytelling, writing in caves, songs, *unyago* and *jando* etc. (Buhori & Lembuka, 2024a).

Realization of Ubuntu education system was made possible by several values that were commonly found in African societies including passion, solidarity, *Ujamaa*, cooperation, human dignity, care, tolerance etc. Literature have proven that each continent is guided by a major philosophy necessary for knowledge and practice toward relevant development, for the case of Africa Ubuntu is a remarkably philosophy that guides Africa knowledge and practice relevant for social work education system despite of being side line by colonial legacy it strongly remained in rural areas and even in urban areas where colonial system didn't work well (Kreitzer & Spitzer, 2019).

With reverence to other Africa societies, Tanzania inherited traditional educational social work knowledge and skills were imparted from one generation to the next generation. A family played a great educational role in conveying the knowledge to the community through traditional means such as storytelling, poems, songs, cave writings and ritual practice etc. (Buhori, 2024a). With more than 130 ethnic tribes in pre-colonial Tanzania yet traditional social work education system capacitated Tanzanians to master their environment through clearing community fields, gender roles, attending sick people, counselling, spiritual services, rules for community peace, maintain acceptable social behaviour, ritual ceremonies, and cultural ethical values (Tanzania Association of Social Workers, 2018). Evidently from literature have shown that existed traditional social work education in pre-colonial Tanzania was designed to serve the most vulnerable groups in the community such as elders, mental challenged persons, women, children, orphans, disabled people, victims of war, and people who were in needy (TESWEP, 2012).

Ujamaa intersections model supported the traditional social work education and practice relevant with African setting designed to serve in the traditional communities (Nyerere, 2011). It helped the community members to master their environment and protect vulnerable populations that were relevant to the improvement of welfare of individuals, families and general community (Lembuka, 2024a). Overtime, Ujamaa intersections model played a vital role of social work education in improving the community welfare through catering the complex needs of the community including hunger, prisoner of wars, sick people, widow, poor, sick people, pregnant women and people addicted with alcohol etc. (Tanzania Association of Social Workers, 2018).

Post Berlin conference of 1884-1885, Tanzania experienced the influx of colonial powers from German to British rule that introduced colonial social work education in the country which represented western social work approaches (Nyerere, 2011). This colonial social work education system did not consider African setting like ecology, history and cultural values rather than serving the interests of few colonial populations in the country especially in urban setting (Mabeyo, 2014). The fact that pre-colonial social work education relied on oral traditions, storytelling, and practical demonstrations, while colonial social work education introduced different the so called formal classroom settings, textbooks, and written examinations etc. (TESWEP, 2012). On the dawn of independence of 1961 the country was under the president of *Mwalimu* Julius Kambarage Nyerere who was the believer and pioneer of African Ubuntu through Ujamaa model that influenced both social work education and social welfare services in the country (Ng'ondi, 2013).

Doubtless the evolution of post-colonial social work education can't be separated from the first president of Tanzania Dr. Nyerere who went further to advocate for Ujamaa intersections model relevant for social work education in African context (Lembuka, 2023b). *Ujamaa* was regarded as national policy through endorsement of a vital Ubuntu tool known as Arusha Declaration of 1967 that emphasized the decolonization of colonial education and restoration of traditional education systems and models (Nyerere, 2011). The Arusha Declaration of 1967, among other goals was to restore decolonise colonial education and replace it with African education systems including traditional social work education (Nyerere, 2011 & Chanila, 2024).

Ujamaa or Community Intersections model became a tool for social work education and practice in Tanzania that represented African Ubuntu where integration of various sections in the

community was necessary for realising sustainable social welfare services (Buhori, 2024). Ujamaa Intersections included family, extended family members, neighbourhood, clan, etc. Every section in Ujamaa intersections model was responsible in acquiring, maintaining, imparting and transferring traditional social welfare education through holistic and collective manner toward the common goals of the community (Nyerere, 2011). To ensure the protection of African interests, the country monopolised social work education on envisioned Ujamaa intersections for 3 decades (Lembuka, 2024c). Ujamaa Ideology was based on the context of asocial protection structure that would see Tanzanians remain equal in terms of horizontal development for all (ASSWOT, 2014).

Despite the remarkable evolution of social work education yet still there are some shortfalls in addressing the complexity of contemporary society that poses significance of establishing this review. More importantly, the emerged schools of social work rendered contextualised competent social workers relevant to address the emerged socio-economic problems in the country including family disintegration, chronic poverty, rising rate of crimes, alcohol and drug abuse, child labour, vulnerable children, HIV & AIDS (TESWEP, 2012). While social welfare system is still influenced by remaining imported colonial social work models yet socio-economic problems have continue to increase the demand for more indigenization of social work education and practice through Ubuntu models like *Ujamaa* (Kreitzer & Spitzer, 2019).

METHODOLOGY

The study is qualitative in nature guided by content analysis of secondary data that involved a process designed to capture pre-identified literature and later condensed into categories or themes based on valid inference and interpretation (Schreier, 2012). The study was further justified by the process of inductive reasoning, by which themes and categories emerged from the data through the researcher's careful examination and constant comparison (Schreier, 2012). The study guided by the Ujamaa Intersection Model to conduct an assessment on the historical advancement of social work education in Tanzania through the *Ubuntu* lens. Content analysis was conducted on existing literature through purposively sampling techniques to identify, exclude, include, analyze, and presentation of the findings. A total of 17 studies and 05 annual reports from Tanzania were purposively selected, screened, and independently reviewed against predetermined criteria for eligibility. The foundation of this review was grounded under the Ujamaa Intersections Model that was thought to be vital in analyzing and presenting the historical advancement of social work education in Tanzania context. Moreover, the justification of the study is supported by the relevance of Ujamaa Intersections model to represent other Indigenous social work education practices in the African context where all aspects of life are envisioned on community's collective and holistic basis through Ubuntu philosophy (Nyerere 2011 & Lembuka, 2024f).

CASE STUDY

The purposive sampling was employed to select Ujamaa or Community Intersections Model of Tanzania as a case study relevant to reflect the historical expansion of social work education in the country (Lembuka, 2024f). Tanzania is a country made up by the Ubuntu union of Tanganyika and Zanzibar that took place on 26th April 1964 (Nyerere, 2011 & Lembuka, 2023d). Selection of Tanzania to justify the historical advancement of social work education in African settings was

thought to be relevant with Ujamaa Policy Framework in post-colonial Tanzania following the Arusha Declaration of 1967. Based on the Ujamaa Policy framework as it was adopted by the country under the influence of the late first President Dr. Julius Kambarage Nyerere-Ubuntu PhD (He preferred to be called Mwalimu or teacher) who embraced African Ubuntu philosophy in post-colonial Tanzania from 1960s through Policy *Ujamaa* (Lembuka, 2024d). Ujamaa amid the core value of African Ubuntu philosophy and Tanzania was the first country to endorse Ubuntu into nation's policy framework in 1967 through the Ujamaa Policy and the policy of self-reliance (Nyerere, 2011 & Lembuka, 2024d). To complement the Ubuntu values and models, Tanzania made several education policy reforms in the country taking consideration of decolonizing education and restoration of African education models (TASWO, 2015). Restoration of the *Ujamaa Intersections* model became a relevant component of social work education that influenced both social work education and practice in the country in the post-colonial Tanzania (Buhori, 2024).

Ujamaa or Community Intersections Model existed from pre-colonial times representing other pre-colonial African Ubuntu Models that went undocumented for centuries but their applicability is doubtless. Existence of Ujamaa Intersections in the community such as neighbourhood, chieftainship, ecology, spirituality and wider attributes depends on the effectiveness of family setting thus the essence of traditional social work education and practice in Tanzania is compatible with *family-hood* (Nyerere, 2011 & Lembuka, 2024f). Amid other sections in the community, family remains to be a custodian and key implementer of all indigenous social work education for the best interests of wider community. Also family connects all major sections in the community towards addressing socio-economic, health and spiritual problems of the community (Mugumbate, 2019). The Ujamaa Intersections Model rendered evidence based platform for discussing indigenous social work education in African context taking a case of post-colonial Tanzania. Despite of being interchangeable, family-hood forms the essence of *Ujamaa Intersections Model* stands for family-hood that for centuries went undocumented.

Table: 1.0 Ujamaa or Community Intersections Model

SN	Level	Linkage to Social Work
1	Family hood/Kaya	Family is responsible for embracing and practice the knowledge of reproduction, home safety, home economics, first aid, parenting and nurturing cultural values
2	Extended family/Relatives	Extended family members are responsible in overseeing the knowledge and practice of family tie, provision of alternative care to vulnerable children, advising, family counselling and mutual support to family in need
3	Neighbourhood	Responsible for the knowledge and practice of immediate support and attend emergence cases and causalities of nearby families like fire outbreak, death, flooding etc. Also, neighbours are responsible for peer grouping, supporting, group work, teamwork and networking

4	Local Leadership	Responsible for settling immediate family disputes within a specific number of households such as 10 cells leaders, shea. Abundant with knowledge of customary laws, and traditional socio-economic and political organization. These are senior citizens and wise men with knowledge of community leadership chosen based on the ethnic tribes or community-based locality
5	Ecology	Knowledge of environmental protection, controlling wild animals, diseases, weather, and sustainable development activities i.e. agriculture, fishing, mining, etc.
6	Spiritual	Knowledge of spiritual power (God, gods, ghosts, and ancestors) necessary for psychosocial care and support
7	Community Wider attributes	This forms the basis of the vision and mission of education based on the collective and holistic current needs of the community

Source: *Lembuka (2024)*

Table 1.0 above renders a comprehensive representation of the traditional social work education in pre and post-colonial through Ujamaa intersections in Tanzania. Ujamaa simply means family hood where other all aspects of life in the community (social, political, economic, and political) are grounded and initiated from the family level (Lembuka, 2024d). Like other Ubuntu education practices in pre-colonial Africa, the Ujama intersection model was informally given meaning no special schools, special teachers, or syllabus which guided learning compared to the Western education system (Buhori, 2024). Every adult in society was a teacher and had the duty to impart traditional social work education of social skills, community welfare and good morals from one generation to another (Lal & Mpangala, 2010).

Ujamaa intersections model of Tanzania represented other Ubuntu traditional social work education systems in African context where knowledge and wisdom of individuals are capacitated and mentored through integrated sections (ASSWOT, 2017 & Lembuka, 2024b). The main principle of Ujamaa intersections was in line with Ubuntu vision of interconnectedness of individuals with their community and the natural world whereby learning was not limited to knowledge but rather it entailed practical experience, skills, cultural values, and ecology (Nyerere, 2011). Over the years Ujamaa intersections remained to be a tool in facilitating the realization of traditional social work knowledge and practice relevant to addressing socio-economic problems and justifiable development in the community (Sheikheldin, 2014 & Lembuka, 2023a).

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The composition of more than 130 ethnic tribes in pre-colonial Tanzania demonstrated a traditional social work education system that was similar founded across other African societies known as

Ubuntu and it was realized through communality, voluntarism, cooperation, human dignity, *Ujamaa* social protection and cultural values etc. (Lal, 2010). *Ubuntu* simply means African humanism or humanness that represents African aspects of life including the social work education component in Africa (Mugumbate 2013). Overtime, the application of the social work education system was compatible with the traditional social welfare demand in African context necessary to master their environment and socio-economic activities in the respective societies through collective and holistic clearing community fields, gender support, mutual support, child protection, attending sick people, counselling, spiritual services, settle disputes, marriage services, community peace, maintain acceptable social behaviour, ritual ceremonies, and cultural ethical values (Mabeyo, 2014 & Asamoah, 2018).

Community support and mutual help were key in traditional social work education in Tanzania and it was imparted to children and youth in various models including traditional rituals like *Unyago* and *Jando* (Leilascafe, 2024). A practical example of Tanzania's traditional rituals can still be obtained among Konde, Yao, Ngoni, Zaramo, Masai, and Guru ethnic tribes, etc. Based on Ubuntu's perspective *Unyago* and *Jando* provided life skills and vocational training that prepared children and youths for adulthood through traditional education, young people acquired communality rather than an individualistic outlook (Leilascafe, 2024). It further emphasized that good manners, human dignity, cleanliness and hygiene, teamwork, hard work, voluntarism, resourcefulness, and abstention from adolescent sex are all important points to consider in the upbringing of adolescents (Leilascafe, 2024).

Moreover, this kind of social work education was instrumental in helping young people to subordinate their interests to those of the wider community and to appreciate the values, norms, and beliefs of their society (Mosweunyane, 2013). This traditional social work education practice went perpendicular with a psychological component which forms a major approach in social work practice including concepts of response conditioning, reward and punishment and repetition formed a core part of educational systems (Mhando et al, 2021). Geographical location and socio-economic activities influenced traditional social work education and practice in pre-colonial Africa (Asamoah, 2018).

Despite the slight differences in Tanzania's traditional social work education system based on the *Ujamaa* approach that represented Ubuntu philosophy (Lembuka, 2023c). This traditional social work education originated and is owned in the local community through the family hood (*Ujamaa*) as a sole custodian of holistic and collective community social welfare (ASSWOT, 2014). The application of the *Ujamaa* traditional social work education system was made possible by *Ujamaa* intersections whereby community organs and structures were responsible at a certain level to embrace and implement social welfare needs. The following is a representation of *Ujamaa* intersections in realization of traditional social work education and practice in Tanzania (Lembuka, 2024c). Social work education and practice experienced a paradigm shift in post-colonial Tanzania, and when the country under the late first president Dr. Julius Kambarage Nyerere (Most people call him Teacher or *Mwalimu*) (DSW, 2013).

Dr. Nyerere advocated and embraced to restore and implement Ubuntu models in education and political administration thus he influenced Tanzania to undergo a series of educational reforms

including social work that aimed at indigenization of social work education and expanding access to education and social welfare services for all citizens (Nyerere, 1967 & 2011). Nyerere introduced education for self-reliance that was relevant with social welfare services in the country in addressing the illiterate gap, adult education, peer group education, team work, self-discipline, life skills, human dignity, ecology, cultural diversity and self-generating income activities etc. (Nyerere, 2011). He further argued that social work approach in post-colonial Tanzania was more urbanized, which had been brought about by European colonialism and was economically driven by wage labour, had disrupted the traditional pre-colonial social work education and practice in reference to rural African society (Sheikheldin, 2014 & Ng'ondi, 2024).

Dr. Nyerere ensured that the government recreate precolonial traditions (social work education and practice) in the country and, in turn, re-established a traditional welfare system through Ujamaa model (Boddy-Evans, 2021). Between 1967 and 1977 the emphasis was on social work education for collective and holistic provision of community social work services under organized families or family-hood (*Ujamaa*) (Nyerere, 2011). The government of Tanzania established communal villages that paved the way for the application of Ujamaa intersections in the provision of community health education, adult education, agricultural training life skills training, and other related social work services. These Ujamaa communes or villages were far in "nucleated" settlements known as *Ujamaa* communes where each commune was composed of around 250 families (Nyerere 2011 & Boddy-Evans, 2021).

Like other African countries, Tanzania is one of the countries with a deep history of traditional social work education and practice from pre-colonial times to the present whereas the Ujamaa intersections Model is among the practical evidence that complements the evidence-based practice. Unfortunately, social work indigenous knowledge and practice in Tanzania and other parts of Africa has insufficient literature equally to other world continents but it goes undocumented. This has offered a room for the provision of traditional social welfare teachings that was based on community needs, cultural values and ecology (Mhando et al, 2021). Despite the reality that there are plenty of surviving writings describing about pre-colonial African educational issues, there is still a quest of information to understand the linkage to social work education (Sheikheldin, 2014). Therefore this review has invested through Ubuntu lens in order to open doors for new insight in understanding and revisiting traditional social work education in Tanzania and other African context where relevant.

Despite the escalating of social work schools from the end of 2000s to date still there are social work schools with training package that do not direct replicate Ujamaa national ideology and cultural values (ASSWOT, 2017). Experience shows that when social work training is not reflecting ecology and culture of respective society that it intends to serve then automatic it faces challenges to manifest its objective towards addressing social, economic, health and political needs (DSW, 2013). Like other African countries, it's not a phenomenon to find some social work training institutions in Tanzania is still embracing the colonial legacy in its composition i.e., theories, models and case studies are western oriented while leaving behind traditional social work

models that represent Ubuntu framework i.e. Ujamaa intersections (Spitzer, 2019 & Lembuka 2024c).

Using imported social work models without considering its application and relevance to African setting is not advisable, this postures a serious challenge for students to apply social work competence during field work placement and later the professional intervention after graduation the society (Kayinga, 2024). According to Spitzer (2019) both social work instruction and practice since colonial time targeted to colonial needs and disregarded African cultural context (Spitzer, 2014). This was further cemented by Mathebane et al (2015) that social work profession has been marginalised and viewed by many as contributing to a destruction of local cultures, wisdom, knowledge, and morals, and ineffective and culturally irrelevant for tackling social challenges in non-Western contexts (Wairire, 2014).

Therefore, being the largest professional social work national organizations in the country TASWO and ASSWOT have no legal mandatory to enforce the indigenization of social work training other than advocating and instructing from a distance (TASWO, 2018 & Ng'ondi, 2024). Also, the lack of national policy and legislation on social work education complements a threat to enforce traditional social work models like *Ujamaa* intersections in the social work training components. Moreover, existing accreditation councils or bodies in the country have inadequate social work experts to ensure the indigenization of social work education in Tanzania

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The review has rendered an evidence-based of the advancement of social work education in Tanzania by presenting historical linkage with pre-colonial and post-colonial social work education. Abundant of empirical findings with Eurocentric perspective makes this study more unique as it presents the first hand findings of Ujamaa Intersections Model while decolonizing existing social work literature for the same. Also, the review is amid few studies that presents Social work education in Tanzania that entails Ubuntu perspective on the formal and informal social work education through Ubuntu lens. Moreover, the capacity of Ujamaa Intersections Model to embrace and demonstrate social work education in Tanzania paramount in understanding the significance contributions of indigenous social work educational models in African context through collective and holistic approach. Lastly, African social work education is originated and practiced by community or Ujamaa sections rather than paper works. Lack of documentation of social work education does not implies there was no existence of social work education and practice in pre-colonial Africa.

Therefore, based on the fact that most of the traditional social work education models went undocumented yet Tanzania's traditional social work education represents other Ubuntu educational models of Africa that are embraced and demonstrated by the community or Ujamaa Intersections from the family level imparted to the wider community settings. To date, *Ujamaa* Intersections Model has remained to be an evidence based social work education model relevant to function within community structures of the contemporary society in addressing the socio-economic complex problems. Basing on the review literature and consultations, author argues to recommend on the following aspects;

- Ujamaa Intersections Model represents other African Ubuntu models has proved to function well with other formal social work education and practice in the African context which renders a call for the decision makers and social work education stakeholders to (re)think the best ways to embrace it through enactment of Ubuntu Policy and related legislations that will complete the indigenization of social work education and practice that will (re)accommodate Ubuntu models like Ujamaa Intersections Model in Tanzania and elsewhere
- Despite of being cost effective model yet Ujamaa Intersections Model has capacity to functions in rural and urban African setting, this compliment with the fact that most of African populations are residing in rural areas. Therefore more integration of Ujamaa Intersections Model in social work education and practice can escalate cost effective social work services in rural areas with Tanzanian populations are residing in rural areas.
- Ujamaa intersections is a practical model that can function well with formal and other informal social work systems to address the current socio-economic problems that other framework has failed to address so far, and this is a call for social work and other experts to integrated Ujamaa intersections Model in social work education models, research and practices
- Existing empirical findings on the historical development of social work education in Tanzania are more Eurocentric than Afrocentric, therefore the review has succeeded to establish gaps that calls for more research in social work education through African Ubuntu lens in the African context

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